

D5.5

Performance Evaluation

OTE

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Performance Evaluation

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Abstract

This document presents the evaluation of the performance and usability of the framework in the context of Task 5.5. The evaluation was performed in two distinct pillars: i) via a user acceptance survey, and ii) based on the elicited requirements

Keywords

Requirements evaluation, performance evaluation, usability, user acceptance survey

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Nature of the deliverable

R

Dissemination level

PU Public, fully open. e.g., website

✓

CL Classified information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

SEN Confidential to DATAMITE project and Commission Services

* Deliverable types:

R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).

DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Abbreviations

ADA	Americans with Disabilities Act
ADLS	Azure Data Lake Storage
AGPL	Affero General Public License
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIM	Agriculture Information Model
AIoD	AI-on-Demand
API	Application Programming Interface
AWS	Amazon Web Services
BUFR	Binary Universal Form for the Representation of meteorological data
C	Compatibility
CO	Compliance
CKAN	Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network
CSV	Comma Separated values
DB	Database
DBMS	Database Management Systems
DCAT	Data Catalogue Vocabulary
DIHs	Digital Innovation Hubs
DM	Data Monetization
DQ	Data Quality
DQV	Data Quality Vocabulary
DS	Data Sharing
DSL	Domain Specific Languages
DSSC	Data Spaces Support Centre
E	Efficiency
EDC	Eclipse Dataspace Connector
EDIH	European Digital Innovation Hub
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
F	Functionality
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FL	Flexibility
G	Governance
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPL	General Public License
I	Interoperability
IAM	Identity and Access Management
ID	Identifier
IDS	International Data Spaces
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IP	Intellectual Property

IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JSON Linked Data
KDE	Key Data Elements
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LLMs	Large Language Models
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
ODRL	Open Digital Rights Language
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OWL	Web Ontology Language
P	Portability
RDBMS	Relational Database Management System
RDF	Resource Description Framework
S	Security
SD	Support & Documentation
SM	Scalability & Maintainability
SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
SO	Sovereignty
SQL	Structured Query Language
STA	SensorThings API
TEF	Testing and Experimentation Facility
U	Usability
UAS	User Acceptance Survey
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VM	Virtual Machine
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WCAG	Web Content Accessibility Guidelines
WP	Work Package
XML	Extensible Markup Language

1 Introduction

DATAMITE is a project funded by the European Commission as part of the Horizon Europe program and coordinated by the ITI - Technological Institute of Informatics. DATAMITE empowers European companies by delivering a modular, open-source and multi-domain Framework to improve DATA Monetizing, Interoperability, Trading and Exchange, in the form of software modules, training, and business materials.

DATAMITE unleashes the monetization potential at two levels. At internal level, users will have tools to improve quality management of their data, adherence to FAIR principles, and will be able to upskill on technical and business aspects thanks to the multiple open-source training materials the project will generate. Therefore, data will become trustable and more reliable also in other paradigms like AI.

At external level, keeping users in control of their data will provide new sources of revenue and interaction with other stakeholders. The architecture envisioned for DATAMITE enables DIHs sandboxing, becoming a potential instructor on their onboarding of SMEs and low-tech SMEs into the data economy. Together, DATAMITE's solutions will function as a catalyst to boost data monetization in the European productive fabric.

1.1 Deliverable Purpose and Scope

Specifically, the Grant Agreement states the following regarding this Deliverable:

Report on the evaluation of the performance and the usability of the DATAMITE Framework.

Hence, the purpose of this document is to present the results of the procedure that was carried out to evaluate the performance and usability of the framework, in the context of Task 5.5. That procedure is twofold: i) evaluation via a user acceptance survey, and ii) assessment based on the requirements that were elicited during the first period of the project.

1.2 Document Structure

This deliverable is broken down into the following sections:

- **Section 1 Introduction** provides the deliverable's general context, dependencies, and structure.
- **Section 0 User Acceptance Survey** describes in detail the survey conducted, including the methodology followed along with the results and their interpretation.

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- **Section 0 Requirement-Based Framework Evaluation** analyzes the assessment of the requirements listed in the deliverable D1.3, that was submitted in M20.
 - **Section 0 Conclusion** summarizes the results of the evaluation process.

Appendixes:

- **Appendix A** depicts the User Acceptance Survey Questionnaire.
- **Appendix B** provides the full Requirements Evaluation Table.

1.3 Document Dependencies

This document depends on deliverable D1.3 Requirements and Architecture (M20), where the complete set of the elicited requirements is listed. It also depends on deliverables D5.2 Report on the Framework Integration and Demonstrator Status (M39) and D5.4 Pilot Demonstrators (M35), which are heavily used as validation sources.

2 User Acceptance Survey

The User Acceptance Survey (UAS) was designed and conducted to evaluate the perceived usability, performance, and overall suitability of the DATAMITE Framework from the perspective of project stakeholders. The structure and content of the questionnaire are described in the following subsections.

2.1 Methodology

The survey was implemented as an online questionnaire and distributed to all DATAMITE consortium partners. Respondents included participants involved in framework development, integration, and validation activities across different work packages and pilot uses cases, covering primarily technical roles with varying levels of familiarity with the framework.

As the DATAMITE framework was accessible exclusively within the consortium during the project, responses were limited to internal stakeholders. This reflects the scope of the evaluation phase, which focused on validation by partners directly involved in the implementation of the framework. External end-user evaluation was not within the scope of this task.

Responses were collected using a structured evaluation scheme based on a four-level ordinal scale (0–3), reflecting the degree of fulfilment of each assessed capability:

- 0 – “Not Fulfilled”
- 1 – “Basic”
- 2 – “Intermediate”
- 3 – “Fulfilled”

For selected performance-related aspects, comparative or stability-oriented scales were used to better reflect real-world usage conditions.

2.2 Questionnaire

The questionnaire was structured into thematic evaluation areas covering the main functional and quality dimensions of the framework. Each section focused on a specific quality attribute or operational capability and was assessed through one or more targeted questions.

The main evaluation domains included:

- **Functionality:** Evaluation of core framework capabilities, coverage of essential requirements, and support for data exploration and monetization-related functions.

- **Flexibility:** Assessment of configurability, customization options, and the ability to extend the framework through modular components.
- **User Friendliness:** Evaluation of ease of installation, configuration, usability, error handling, accessibility, and multilingual support.
- **Support & Documentation:** Assessment of the availability, clarity, and usefulness of documentation and support materials.
- **Scalability & Maintainability:** Evaluation of performance under increasing data volumes and user loads, stability, and API maturity.
- **Efficiency & Performance:** Assessment of automation support, parallel task handling, system stability, and responsiveness.
- **Interoperability & Compatibility:** Evaluation of standards support, integration with external systems, deployment environments, and API availability.
- **Portability:** Assessment of data and workflow portability across platforms and formats.
- **Security, Data Protection and compliance:** Evaluation of access control, encryption, auditing, legal compliance, and domain-specific regulatory support.
- **Governance, Sovereignty, and IPR:** Assessment of governance mechanisms, policy enforcement, data sovereignty, ownership, and intellectual property rights management.
- **Data Quality and Data Monetization:** Evaluation of data quality monitoring, validation, usage tracking, and monetization-related functionalities.

A complete list of survey questions and scales is provided in the Appendix A: User Acceptance Survey Questionnaire.

2.3 Quantitative Results

Given the project scope, the DATAMITE framework was accessible exclusively to project partners for testing and validation purposes. Consequently, the User Acceptance Survey was conducted internally, as only project participants had the necessary access to provide meaningful feedback. The User Acceptance Survey collected responses from 29 participants representing project partners involved in the development, integration, and validation of the DATAMITE framework.

The aggregated results indicate a generally positive perception of the framework across the evaluated criteria. Across all evaluated questions, 64%¹ of responses indicate that the assessed capability is “Fulfilled”, while 26% correspond to an “Intermediate” level of fulfilment. A further 7% of responses indicate a “Basic” level of implementation, and only 1% indicate that the evaluated capability is “Not fulfilled”.

In parallel, the survey explicitly allowed respondents to select “I don’t know” where they did not have sufficient familiarity with a specific aspect; missing responses were also considered within this category. When analysed by domain, these responses vary across categories, reflecting differences in respondent exposure to specific framework components. The proportion of “I don’t know” and missing responses was calculated per evaluation domain relative to the total number of responses recorded within each domain. The results show a varying level of familiarity across domains, with values ranging from approximately 26% to 67%. Lower levels of uncertainty are observed in domains such as Functionality and Flexibility, indicating broader exposure among respondents. In contrast, higher proportions are found in domains such as Sovereignty and Compliance, which are associated with more specialized or less frequently used components of the framework. The full set of survey responses (raw data) and the corresponding aggregated results are available through the [Evaluation of Usability & Performance Survey Dataset](#) for reference and traceability.

¹ Responses marked as “I don’t know” and missing answers were excluded from the maturity level calculation

Figure 1: Distribution of survey responses by maturity level based on valid evaluations from project partners, highlighting the overall perceived implementation maturity of the DATAMITE framework.

2.4 Interpretation of Survey Results

The survey results provide several insights regarding the perceived performance and usability of the DATAMITE framework. The high proportion of responses classified as “Fulfilled” indicates that the framework successfully delivers its functionalities. This is supported by participant feedback highlighting that key capabilities such as dataset ingestion, data profiling, metadata management, and data product dissemination are operational and effectively support expected use cases.

Responses categorised as “Intermediate” mainly reflect areas where the framework already provides functional support but where additional refinements, usability improvements, or extended operational scenarios could further enhance the user experience. These responses therefore highlight opportunities for incremental improvements rather than structural limitations.

In particular, participant comments point to aspects such as deployment complexity, configuration of interactions between components, performance when processing large datasets, and the need for clearer error handling or more user-friendly. Similarly, certain advanced features such as access control, governance mechanisms, interoperability with external data spaces, or

monetisation functionalities were not consistently tested across all partners, contributing to more moderate assessments.

“Basic” responses point to limited areas for improvement, while the negligible proportion of not fulfilled responses confirms the absence of major functional gaps. The presence of “I don’t know” responses further indicates that some domains were outside the direct experience of certain respondents, particularly for specialised or less frequently used functionalities, rather than reflecting shortcomings of the framework itself.

Overall, the results indicate that the framework is perceived as a functionally mature and operationally usable solution, aligned with the objectives of the DATAMITE project.

To complement this perception-based evaluation, a second validation layer based on requirement coverage analysis was introduced, as described in the following section.

3 Requirement-Based Framework Evaluation

In addition to the User Acceptance Survey (UAS), a second validation layer was introduced in order to strengthen the robustness, transparency, and consistency of the overall evaluation process. This layer was implemented through a structured Excel-based assessment table designed to systematically map the defined project requirements to the implemented framework components.

While the UAS primarily captures stakeholder perceptions, usability impressions, and experiential feedback regarding the framework, the secondary validation layer provides a complementary analytical perspective. It enables a requirement-oriented evaluation that supports the cross-verification and consolidation of the survey findings with evidence-based implementation data.

Within this assessment framework, requirement owners reviewed each of the 154 project requirements and evaluated their implementation status within the final system architecture. For each requirement, the degree of coverage was assessed (covered, partially covered, or not covered), and supporting evidence was documented through a dedicated validation source field. This field provides traceable references to the corresponding implementation artefacts, pilot deployments, documentation, or operational validation activities.

By combining requirement coverage assessment with traceable validation sources, this second validation layer ensures a systematic verification of whether the defined project requirements are implemented, to what extent they are fulfilled, and which concrete evidence supports their validation.

3.1 Methodology

The Excel-based validation table was distributed to the respective requirement owners across the project consortium. Each partner was responsible for reviewing and validating the requirements associated with the components or modules under their responsibility. The set of evaluated requirements is based on the consolidated list defined in WP1 in T1.3, where functional and non-functional requirements were collected, analysed, and validated at the project level. These requirements were not defined by individual component owners during the validation phase, but originate from a common, previously agreed baseline. For each requirement, partners were asked to assess the current implementation status based on the final system architecture and the results obtained during the pilot deployments and technical validations. The assessment was performed

using a predefined classification scheme consisting of the following categories: “Covered”, “Partially Covered”, “Not Covered”, and “Not Applicable”.

- **Covered:** the requirement is fully implemented and operational within the framework.
- **Partially Covered:** the requirement is implemented to a certain extent, but additional refinements are ongoing.
- **Not Covered:** the requirement is not implemented in the current system.
- **Not Applicable:** the requirement is not relevant to the final system configuration or falls outside the implemented scope. For example, certain requirements related to components or functionalities not included in the final deployment configuration were classified as “Not Applicable”, as they do not apply to the implemented system rather than representing missing functionality.

In addition to the coverage status, partners were required to provide a validation source for each assessed requirement. This field allowed the documentation of supporting evidence, such as implementation references, pilot deployment results, documentation links, or operational validation activities. The inclusion of this field ensured traceability of the assessment and strengthened the transparency of the validation process.

The completed tables were subsequently consolidated and analyzed in order to produce a global overview of requirement coverage across the framework. This analysis enabled the identification of fully implemented requirements, partially covered elements requiring further refinement, and the limited number of requirements not addressed within the final system configuration.

Overall, this structured validation approach complements the User Acceptance Survey by providing a systematic, requirement-level verification of the implemented framework and ensuring consistency between the defined specifications and the realized system capabilities.

The consolidated results of the requirement owner validation are presented in the following subsection, offering a quantitative overview of the degree of requirement coverage within the implemented framework.

3.2 Quantitative Overview

A total of 154 requirements were assessed within the second validation layer (Figure 2). The evaluation shows that 114 requirements (74%) are fully covered by the implemented system. In addition, 25 requirements (16%) are partially covered, indicating that the core functionality has

been implemented while certain refinements, extensions, or broader validation scenarios remain ongoing.

Only 3 requirements (2%) are marked as not covered. According to the partner assessments, these cases are primarily related to scope adaptations or dependencies on external components that were not included in the final system configuration and therefore do not affect the structural integrity of the framework.

Furthermore, 12 requirements (8%) were classified as not applicable in the final system configuration, reflecting elements that were either superseded by architectural refinements or considered outside the operational scope of the deployed solution.

Figure 2: Requirements Coverage

3.3 High-Level Analysis of “Partially Covered” Requirements

Out of the 154 assessed requirements, 25 are marked as partially covered. A review of the partner comments indicates that partial coverage generally reflects incremental implementation stages rather than missing core functionality.

In most cases, the fundamental technical capability has already been implemented, while further refinements, extended integration scenarios, or documentation formalisation remain ongoing. Some entries also correspond to functionalities validated within specific pilot environments rather than across all potential operational scenarios.

Importantly, none of the partially covered requirements compromises the structural integrity, security, or compliance of the system. Instead, they represent controlled system evolution and iterative enhancement, which is consistent with the progressive maturity of the framework.

3.4 High-Level Analysis of “Not Covered” Requirements

Only three requirements are marked as not covered. According to the partner explanations provided in the validation table, these cases are primarily linked to scope adaptations, architectural refinements, or dependencies on external components that were not included in the final system deployment.

These deviations do not affect the core architecture, regulatory compliance, or security mechanisms of the framework. Their limited number and clearly documented justification confirm that they do not introduce structural risks.

Overall, the very small number and low criticality of not covered requirements further support the stability and completeness of the implemented system version.

3.5 Prioritisation-Based Evaluation

As stated in D1.3, DATAMITE project has elicited both mandatory and optional requirements according to MoSCoW methodology. For mandatory requirements (MUST and SHOULD), different thresholds have been defined for success evaluation:

- 90% for MUST requirements
- 75% for SHOULD requirements

The prioritisation-based evaluation of the project is considered successful if both above thresholds are fulfilled. To calculate the score for each priority level, the following assumptions have been made:

- Requirements that are marked as “Not Applicable” are not considered.

- As the MoSCoW methodology provides prioritisation but does not define quantitative evaluation metrics, a simple weighted scoring formula was adopted, where the percentage of the “Partially Covered” requirements is multiplied by 0.5. The selection of a 0.5 factor for partial coverage is supported by multiple studies in the literature, which follow similar intermediate weighting approaches²³⁴. In our case, it is a rather modest factor since, as mentioned in subsection 3.3, partial coverage generally reflects incremental implementation stages rather than missing core functionality.

Figure 3: MUST Requirements Coverage

² <https://ijain.org/index.php/IJAIN/article/view/1082/pdf>

³ <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10462-023-10667-1>

⁴ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2215016122002746>

Figure 4: SHOULD Requirements Coverage

Figure 3 and Figure 4 depict the requirements percentage coverage for MUST and SHOULD requirements, respectively. Based on the coverage scores provided in Table 1, both thresholds have been achieved.

Table 1: Prioritisation-based coverage score (baseline approach)

Priority Level	Coverage Score	Threshold	Fulfilled
MUST	90.5%	90%	YES
SHOULD	88%	75%	YES

The above approach to calculate the requirements coverage score follows a baseline (monolithic) scoring model, in which requirement fulfilment is assessed using a fixed weighting scheme: fully covered requirements are assigned a value of 1, partially covered requirements a value of 0.5, and non-covered requirements a value of 0. This approach provides a simple and transparent aggregate measure of coverage and aligns with commonly used practices in evaluation frameworks, where partial fulfilment is represented through proportional weighting.

However, due to the marginal outcome concerning the requirements of MUST priority, an additional approach has been implemented, particularly for those requirements. That second approach is a more analytical (granular) assessment, in which partially covered requirements are not treated uniformly but are instead evaluated individually. In detail, each partially covered requirement is assigned a weight within a distinct range (e.g., 0.1 – 0.3, 0.4 – 0.6, or 0.7 – 0.9), depending on its degree of completion, or if is associated to a specific pilot etc. Requirements that are nearly complete and operational are assigned higher weights, whereas those with significant gaps or limited usability receive lower weights. (Not covered requirements are again assigned a value 0). The analytical approach is not needed for SHOULD requirements, since even in the worst-case scenario (factor close to 0) the coverage score is 79%, still above the 75% defined threshold.

This dual approach allows for both comparability and interpretability: the baseline model ensures consistency and ease of communication, while the analytical model captures the heterogeneity of partial fulfilment and provides a more nuanced assessment of the framework’s completeness. Furthermore, the analytical approach supports sensitivity analysis by demonstrating how variations in the treatment of partial coverage influence the overall evaluation outcome.

Table 2 depicts the comments and the factor range that are assigned to each one partially covered MUST requirement. The range (and the comments) is determined based on the notes written in Table 3, which describe the level of completion, at least for all partially, not covered, and not applicable requirements.

Table 2: Analysis of partially covered MUST requirements

Requirement ID	Description	Comment	Factor Range
R021	The framework must provide mechanisms for data harmonisation	The functionality is completed, lacking only direct incorporation into the framework	0.7 – 0.9

Requirement ID	Description	Comment	Factor Range
R046	As a data provider/provider of domain service, I would like to validate if the data are following the standard/ontology (like AIM in the case of the agriculture domain)	The moderate level of functionality is completed, but it is related to a specific pilot	0.7 - 0.9
R067	The connectors from the data sharing module that will be implemented in the pilot 4 must be able to provide information from the company database to the (energy) data space in order to explore new ways of providing this information	Issues are not related to DATAMITE per se. In addition, it affects a specific pilot	0.7 – 0.9
R073	As the provider of domain service in agriculture, I would like to setup, configure and customise the Catalogue of DATAMITE framework based on DATAMITE components	The moderate level of functionality is completed, but it is related to a specific pilot	0.7 – 0.9

Requirement ID	Description	Comment	Factor Range
R112	Interfaces to compare the quality of different datasets, considering a future provision to third parties, through exchange or sale	The moderate level of functionality is completed	0.4 – 0.6
R143	A connector to the company data lake must be developed in the data support tools module in order to ingest and process the datasets for the pilot 4	The functionality is completed, testing is pending. In addition, it affects a specific pilot	0.7 – 0.9
R152	We must have multiple user tiers, with multiple roles associated. Users must be able to create an account (at least for the lower tier). Others would be managed by admins	The minimum level of functionality is completed	0.1 – 0.3
R183	Training material that enables companies better understanding the roles and responsibilities of individual internal departments within the data cycle	The functionality is completed, but the corresponding training material is missing	0.1 – 0.3

Requirement ID	Description	Comment	Factor Range
R187	The platform must be compliant with ADA and WCAG under European guidelines	At the end of the development stages, these metrics are being constantly enhanced	0.4 – 0.6
R193	In order to deploy the demonstration, a Azure-base sandbox must be created in the E-REDES IT systems	The functionality is completed, testing is pending. In addition, it affects a specific pilot	0.7 – 0.9

The average factor range is 0.52 – 0.72, so the range for the coverage score is calculated as follows: $83\% + 0.52 \cdot 15\% - 83\% + 0.72 \cdot 15\% = 90.8\% - 93.8\%$, still above the 90% defined threshold in any case.

3.6 Overall Assessment

The second validation layer demonstrates strong alignment between the defined project requirements and the implemented system capabilities. The high proportion of fully covered requirements (74%) indicates that the core functionality has been implemented in the vast majority of cases. The very limited proportion of not covered requirements (2%), together with their transparent documented justification, confirms that these do not affect the structural integrity or operational completeness of the framework.

The prioritisation-based evaluation further reinforces these findings. The coverage baseline scores achieved for both MUST (90.5%) and SHOULD (88%) requirements exceed the defined success thresholds, confirming that the framework meets its critical and high-priority requirements.

The structured requirement owner validation process was supported by traceable validation sources, which record the basis on which each requirement was assessed. These sources include, among others, direct involvement in the development, testing results, pilot implementation or pilot testing experience, operational usage, technical documentation, and, where relevant, external references or repository links. This explicit evidence layer strengthens

the traceability of the assessment and makes the justification of requirement fulfilment across the framework more transparent and reliable.

4 Conclusion

This deliverable presents a comprehensive evaluation of the performance, usability, and implementation maturity of the DATAMITE framework, combining two complementary assessment approaches: a User Acceptance Survey capturing stakeholder perceptions, and a requirement-based framework evaluation providing a structured, evidence-based validation of system capabilities.

The results of the User Acceptance Survey indicate a consistently positive perception of the framework across all evaluated dimensions. The high proportion of responses classified as “Fulfilled” and “Intermediate” confirms that the framework is considered by project stakeholders as functionally capable, operationally usable, with no major functional gaps identified.

At the same time, the evaluation provides a balanced view of the framework’s current state:

Strengths

- High requirement coverage, including fulfilment of critical requirements above defined thresholds.
- Core functionalities validated through pilot implementations and testing activities.
- Traceable validation supported by explicit evidence sources.
- Positive user perception across usability and performance dimensions.
- Modular architecture supporting interoperability and heterogeneous data integration.

The evaluation was conducted in parallel with the ongoing development and evolution of the framework, which explains part of the identified limitations and reflects the progressive maturation of the system:

Limitations

- Deployment and configuration remain technically demanding in some cases.
- Some functionalities are only partially covered due to ongoing refinements or external dependencies.
- Certain advanced features are not fully validated across all scenarios.
- Uneven respondent familiarity across domains, reflected in “I don’t know” responses

The combination of both evaluation approaches provides a coherent and validated assessment of the DATAMITE framework. While the survey reflects user experience and practical usability, the requirement-based analysis ensures traceability and validation of implementation

completeness. Together, they confirm that the framework has reached a mature and operational state, capable of supporting data monetisation, interoperability, and data governance use cases, while also identifying areas for further refinement beyond the project scope.

Appendix A: User Acceptance Survey

Questionnaire

DATAMITE Framework Results – Evaluation of Usability & Performance

Functionality

1. Is the framework already being tested or used?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled	Basic	Intermediate	Fulfilled	I don't know
<input type="radio"/>				

2. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

3. Does the framework cover all essential requirements, including support for data exploration and providing meaningful overviews of datasets (e.g. structure, fields, basic summaries) to help users understand data before use?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled	Basic	Intermediate	Fulfilled	I don't know
<input type="radio"/>				

4. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

5. Does it support functions such as "Access Restriction", "Payment Interfaces" and "Licence Management"?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled	Basic	Intermediate	Fulfilled	I don't know
<input type="radio"/>				

6. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

Flexibility

7. Can the framework be configured and customized (e.g. catalogue, components, policies) to support specific purposes or business goals?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled	Basic	Intermediate	Fulfilled	I don't know
<input type="radio"/>				

8. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

9. Does it have a modular structure to enable future extensions?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled	Basic	Intermediate	Fulfilled	I don't know
<input type="radio"/>				

10. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

User Friendliness

11. Is the framework easy to install, initialize, configure and use?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled

Basic

Intermediate

Fulfilled

I don't know

12. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

13. Does the framework recognise and explain errors?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled

Basic

Intermediate

Fulfilled

I don't know

14. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

15. Does it load quickly and process data efficiently?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled

Basic

Intermediate

Fulfilled

I don't know

16. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

17. Is the framework accessible for all users and does it work / support different languages (EU)?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

- Not Fulfilled Basic Intermediate Fulfilled I don't know

18. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

Support & Documentation

19. Are the documentation and support tools helpful and easy to understand?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

- Not Fulfilled Basic Intermediate Fulfilled I don't know

20. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

Scalability & Maintainability

21. Compared to existing solutions you are familiar with, how would you assess the framework's ability when processing large volumes of data during typical tasks (e.g. ingestion, querying, data exchange) and under realistic usage conditions?

0: Significantly worse; 1: Slightly worse; 2: Comparable; 3: Better

- Significantly worse Slightly worse Comparable Better I don't know
-

22. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

23. When exposed to higher loads (more users or more data), how did the framework behave in terms of stability and responsiveness?

0: Unstable or unusable; 1: Stable with significant performance loss; 2: Stable with minor performance loss; 3: Stable with no noticeable performance loss

- Unstable or unusable Stable with significant performance loss Stable with minor performance loss Stable with no noticeable performance loss I don't know
-

24. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

25. How stable is the API? Are there regular, secure releases?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

- Not Fulfilled Basic Intermediate Fulfilled I don't know
-

26. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

Efficiency

27. Does the framework support automation processes (e.g. monitoring, logging)?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled	Basic	Intermediate	Fulfilled	I don't know
<input type="radio"/>				

28. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

29. Does it handle multiple tasks/requests simultaneously?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled	Basic	Intermediate	Fulfilled	I don't know
<input type="radio"/>				

30. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

31. Is it stable enough to minimize outages?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled	Basic	Intermediate	Fulfilled	I don't know
<input type="radio"/>				

32. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

Interoperability

33. Does the framework support common standards and protocols?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled Basic Intermediate Fulfilled I don't know

34. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

35. Is it possible to integrate it seamlessly with other systems and data sources?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled Basic Intermediate Fulfilled I don't know

36. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

Compatibility

37. Is the framework compatible with multiple operating systems, platforms, or database technologies?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled Basic Intermediate Fulfilled I don't know

38. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

39. Does the framework provide standardised APIs that enable integration with external systems and tools?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled	Basic	Intermediate	Fulfilled	I don't know
<input type="radio"/>				

40. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

41. Can the framework operate in cloud, on-premise, and hybrid environments without restrictions?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled	Basic	Intermediate	Fulfilled	I don't know
<input type="radio"/>				

42. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

Portability

43. Does the framework support transferring datasets and metadata to other platforms or tools?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled	Basic	Intermediate	Fulfilled	I don't know
<input type="radio"/>				

44. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

45. Does the framework enable data-portable formats (e.g., JSON-LD, CSV, DCAT, RDF)?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled Basic Intermediate Fulfilled I don't know

46. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

47. Can processes or workflows defined inside the framework be exported or reused in other environments?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled Basic Intermediate Fulfilled I don't know

48. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

Security & Data Protection

49. Does the framework provide robust security mechanisms, such as access control, encryption and anonymization?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled Basic Intermediate Fulfilled I don't know

50. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

51. Does it support data protection requirements and compliance ?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled	Basic	Intermediate	Fulfilled	I don't know
<input type="radio"/>				

52. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

53. Does the framework include tools for monitoring and auditing transactions to ensure transparency with external users?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled	Basic	Intermediate	Fulfilled	I don't know
<input type="radio"/>				

54. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

Data Sharing

55. Does the framework provide continuous monitoring and reporting mechanisms to enforce and assess data usage conditions (e.g. restrictions, purpose limitation, usage policies), and to support transparency and governance of data sharing?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled	Basic	Intermediate	Fulfilled	I don't know
<input type="radio"/>				

56. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

57. Does the framework provide logging, usage monitoring, and accounting or telemetry mechanisms for data sharing (e.g. access logs, usage statistics, reporting) to support transparency and potential billing or data valuation?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled	Basic	Intermediate	Fulfilled	I don't know
<input type="radio"/>				

58. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

59. Does the framework support consent management and contractual agreement handling for data sharing, including the definition, storage, and visibility of usage contracts and agreed policies?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled	Basic	Intermediate	Fulfilled	I don't know
<input type="radio"/>				

60. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

61. Does the framework ensure integrity, traceability, and trust throughout the data sharing process (e.g. integrity of shared data, agreements, and related transactions)?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled	Basic	Intermediate	Fulfilled	I don't know
<input type="radio"/>				

62. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

Data Quality

63. Is the framework capable of monitoring and improving data quality?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled	Basic	Intermediate	Fulfilled	I don't know
<input type="radio"/>				

64. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

65. Does the framework provide tools for data profiling and quality assessment, including indicators and checks such as completeness, validity, timeliness, consistency, missing or inconsistent data, anomalies/outliers, and detection of quality changes (e.g. concept drift)?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled	Basic	Intermediate	Fulfilled	I don't know
<input type="radio"/>				

66. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

67. Does the framework support automatic validation or anomaly detection for datasets?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled	Basic	Intermediate	Fulfilled	I don't know
<input type="radio"/>				

68. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

Governance

69. Does the framework offer governance functions such as metadata management through a data catalogue (including editing and enrichment of data asset information, linking data entities or fields to glossary terms), as well as versioning and audit logs?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled Basic Intermediate Fulfilled I don't know

70. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

71. Does the framework provide a clear governance structure for managing datasets, metadata, policies and responsibilities?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled Basic Intermediate Fulfilled I don't know

72. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

73. Does the framework enforce governance policies (access rules, quality rules, update rules) consistently?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled Basic Intermediate Fulfilled I don't know

74. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

Compliance

75. Is it compliant with legal requirements (GDPR, Data Act, etc ...)?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled	Basic	Intermediate	Fulfilled	I don't know
<input type="radio"/>				

76. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

77. Does the framework ensure traceability of all data operations in a legally auditable manner?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled	Basic	Intermediate	Fulfilled	I don't know
<input type="radio"/>				

78. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

79. Does the framework support domain-specific compliance (industry standards, contractual requirements)?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled	Basic	Intermediate	Fulfilled	I don't know
<input type="radio"/>				

80. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

Sovereignty

81. Does the framework support the definition and enforcement of different usage policies for data access and use?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled

Basic

Intermediate

Fulfilled

I don't know

82. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

83. What mechanisms are in place to preserve ownership rights and ensure transparency in the data market? How does the framework ensure data sovereignty is maintained?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled

Basic

Intermediate

Fulfilled

I don't know

84. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

85. Does the framework include tools for securely storing usage contracts?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled

Basic

Intermediate

Fulfilled

I don't know

86. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)

87. Does the framework allow defining ownership and usage rights for datasets?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

- Not Fulfilled Basic Intermediate Fulfilled I don't know
-

88. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

89. Are licensing conditions for published/shared datasets clearly represented?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

- Not Fulfilled Basic Intermediate Fulfilled I don't know
-

90. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

91. Does the framework support the management of contractual usage rights with external partners?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

- Not Fulfilled Basic Intermediate Fulfilled I don't know
-

92. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

Data Monetisation

93. Does the framework support publishing or advertising datasets on European data marketplaces?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled

Basic

Intermediate

Fulfilled

I don't know

94. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

95. Does the framework clearly show the policies, licenses, or contractual conditions agreed between users and data providers?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled

Basic

Intermediate

Fulfilled

I don't know

96. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

97. Does the framework provide usage statistics (downloads, contracts, transactions)?

0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled

Basic

Intermediate

Fulfilled

I don't know

98. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

99. Does the framework allow viewing and managing data access policies defined by data providers?
0: Not Fulfilled; 1: Basic; 2: Intermediate; 3: Fulfilled

Not Fulfilled	Basic	Intermediate	Fulfilled	I don't know
<input type="radio"/>				

100. Comment & Notes

Enter your answer

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Appendix B: Requirements Evaluation Table

Table 3 depicts in detail the evaluation of each one requirement, including its relation to the UAS questions (Appendix A), the assessment, as well as the validation source. More specifically, the Survey Question IDs indicate the question(s) category and the specific question(s) under this category. For example, F-c refers to the third question concerning Functionality category. For the requirements that need further explanation for the assessment, additional notes are provided (at least for all Partially, Not covered, and Not applicable requirements).

Table 3: Requirements Evaluation Table

ID	Description	Survey Question IDs	Assessment	Validation Source	Notes
R007	The framework could provide the option to sell data according to various charging methods	F-c	Not applicable		Deemed out of scope
R009	The connectors from the data sharing module could be able to provide the pilot 4 data requesters characteristics in order to implement data access policies	DS-a	Covered	Direct involvement in development	Through the policy engine, integrated with the EDC connector, and the 3 policies developed (Time interval, Location, and Purpose)
R011	The Data sharing module should allow publishing/advertising datasets to European Data Platforms and Markets (such as AIoD or EOSC)	DM-a	Partially covered	Testing results, Pilot testing	EOSC support was not implemented due to unavailability of the platform. Instead, other platforms were supported such as CKAN/Mistral, OpenData portal, Mistral, Pontus X
R012	As a data provider, I want to be able to select in which European Platforms to publish the metadata of my dataset(s)	DM-a, P-a	Covered	Testing results, Pilot testing	
R013	The data logging tool from the data sharing module	DM-c, DS-b	Covered	Direct involvement in	

	should provide and/or quantify data usage metrics (direct metrics, metrics of data shared by other providers/users, consumption (download) in order to analyze the benefits of sharing data			development, Testing results	
R014	As the provider of domain service in agriculture, I would like to understand the statistics about the data usage (downloads, contracts) and have information about the clients and their profile, to improve the offer and user experience and better targeting the clients	DM-c	Not applicable	Pilot implementation experience (Pilot 5) and testing results	Apparently, there are no statistics from the data portals about the data published in DATAMITE
R015	As a data provider, I want to be able to set a price for each license/usage policy (including free access, meaning zero price)	F-c	Partially covered	Direct involvement in the brokers development	Can be specified on the published records published on the marketplace
R016	As a data provider, I want to be able to see the agreed policies (purchased contracts) for my dataset(s)	DM-b, F-c, IPR-b	Covered	Direct involvement in development	
R017	As a user, I want to be able to see the data access policies I agreed to (contracts I purchased)	DS-c	Covered	Direct involvement in development	
R018	As a user, I want to be able to see the resources I can still consume (download) according to my agreed policies (contracts)	DM-c	Not applicable	Direct involvement in development, Testing results	DATAMITE is a framework with a primary emphasis on data providers rather than data consumers
R019	The framework requires a data glossary that can be used to define different vocabularies (probably coming from different domains), composed of terms that define concepts in a univocal way (to make	I-a	Covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	The number of business vocabularies in the data glossary is not limited. New vocabularies can be added at any point to the

	easier for companies to use a single term for each concept)				glossary. Similarly, vocabularies can be extended with new terms at any moment
R020	The framework should be able to establish relations between terms of different vocabularies	I-a	Covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	Synonyms and Antonyms can be defined. These are basic relations and could be easily extended to others
R021	The framework must provide mechanisms for data harmonization	I-a	Partially covered	Pilot implementation experience (Pilot 5) and testing results	Services connect to DATAMITE framework, and follow DATAMITE layout, but are not within framework
R022	The framework must utilize ontologies and standard modeling vocabularies for improved interoperability	I-a, G-a	Not covered	Pilot implementation experience (Pilot 5) and testing results	There are no standard ontologies / vocabularies directly used by the framework. However, data harmonization allows the usage of these for improved interoperability
R023	As a data hub provider/domain provider, I would like to provide the data harmonized in a standardized and interoperable way, making it compatible on syntax and semantic level, so that its usage can be maximized by other providers and potential users in the domain	I-a, P-b	Covered	Pilot implementation experience (Pilot 5) and testing results	DATAMITE brings various tools for data harmonization
R024	The framework must design an internal metadata model that covers various aspects (e.g., data quality) and is informative	I-a	Covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	There is an internal metadata model defined, based on DCAT and cross-domain

R025	The framework should organize model terms in glossaries for better clarity and reference	I-a	Covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	There is a data glossary that allows for the creation, edition and deletion of vocabularies. Each vocabulary aggregates business terms that can be used to enrich datasets.
R026	The framework should enable registration of metadata representations with dedicated broker services	I-b	Covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	Metadata is stored following a common schema for datasets, data products or publications. The metadata schema is mapped to third-party schemas in order to publish the assets in remote ecosystems through specific brokers/plugins.
R027	The Data Quality Module must be independent of any data-source format	DQ-c	Not applicable / Covered indirectly	Direct involvement in development	By utilizing the KPI-library module, the Data Quality Module can support any format provided.
R028	Different data formats such as JSON, CSV and XML could be normalized to the internal data model (compliant to BUFR specifications) enabling a unified schema ingestion	P-b	Partially covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	There are several formats accepted (CSV, JSON, etc.). BUFR was not finally considered as necessary. It would be accepted, though, although it would not be profiled.
R029	The Data Quality Module should have an open API, so that new big vendors & providers can benefit and	C-b	Covered	Direct involvement in development	All DATAMITE components, including the Data Quality Module, are free and open

	have the ability to publish and extend their services				source with open API specifications
R030	The Data Quality Module component should be Big Data compliant	DQ-c	Covered	Operational Usage, Testing results	Data Quality Module is based on Spark Clusters for Big Data compliance.
R031	The pilot data should follow a specific structured format (e.g., DB schema, CSV file) especially for data harmonization purposes	I-a	Covered	Direct involvement in development	The data should be provided in a CSV structured format, which is supported by the ICCS Harmonization module.
R032	For data harmonization purposes, the pilot data values of non-numeric fields should belong to either local or international terminologies, classifications, vocabularies or coding systems, with the terms being well described in a format that both humans and software agents can understand	I-a	Covered	Direct involvement in development	The harmonization process will work better with well-defined vocabularies and specifications for data values (supports OWL ontologies)
R033	The framework should provide/support the appropriate metadata models for also capturing all the important parameters of pilot data and their features for data harmonization purposes	I-a	Covered	Direct involvement in development	The ICCS Harmonization Module is extracting all appropriate metadata from the artifacts in order to facilitate the process
R035	The Data support tools should provide means for data and metadata harmonization based on a given description	I-b; CO-b	Covered	Direct involvement in development, Testing results	The ICCS Harmonization module does indeed provide these harmonization functionalities.
R037	Each dataset should be accompanied by a common schema of metadata	I-a	Covered	Participated in the	All datasets are described following the same metadata schema, which

				development. Validated.	facilitates its ulterior sharing or publication
R038	The data model of the dataset metadata in the DATAMITE Catalogue must contain all fields needed to publish to the selected data markets	P-a	Covered	Testing results, Pilot testing	
R039	The framework must internally store the pilot metadata in accordance with the metadata model developed	I-a, G-a	Covered	Direct involvement in development. Testing results.	All metadata is stored internally in a metadata repository (Apache Atlas) following a common metadata schema developed within the project and aligned with standards such as DCAT or DQV. This includes the metadata related to pilot data.
R042	The Data sharing module should allow the user to publish data to open-source repositories like OpenML or Zenodo in easy manner	DM-a	Covered	Testing results, Pilot testing	
R044	As a data provider, I would be interested to provide information about the underlying data models and ontologies used by the published data as part of its metadata, so that consumers of my data can understand it better, e.g., what are the fields, what are their meaning, what are the units of measurement used, etc.	G-a	Partially covered	Pilot implementation experience and testing results	The glossary of terms can be defined, but there is no direct connection to ontologies / data models
R045	End users should have the capability to access data products offered by different data providers and the response of the outcomes	DS-d, S-b	Partially Covered	Pilot implementation experience and testing results	Within the same DATAMITE framework instance access to other data products by

	should be retrieved during a timeframe that will allow business to operate as usual				different data providers can be achieved, depending on the access rules configured for data products
R046	As a data provider/provider of domain service, I would like to validate if the data are following properly the standard/ontology (like AIM in the case of the agriculture domain)	I-a	Partially covered	Pilot implementation experience (Pilot 5) and testing results	Only the glossary of terms can be defined, but there is no direct connection to ontologies/data models
R047	As a DATAMITE developer, I want the DATAMITE Catalogue to have an open API, so that I can use it to find datasets and obtain their metadata	C-b, I-b	Not applicable	Direct involvement in the brokers development	Initial request meant to access the metadata to be published on the marketplace. The implementation changed and all the necessary data is passed to the broker.
R048	The platform should offer APIs and data connectors to enable seamless integration with external applications, facilitating data exchange and analysis	I-b	Covered	Pilot integration and implementation experience and testing results. Direct involvement	
R049	As agriculture data provider as part of Pilot 5: Connecting eDWIN to Data Markets, I would like to transform existing data into AIM (Agriculture Information Model)-compliant format, to enable other systems to consume it	I-a	Covered	Pilot implementation experience (Pilot 5) and testing results	We use data harmonization pipelines
R050	As agriculture service provider, as part of Pilot 5: Connecting eDWIN to Data Markets, I would like to generate AIM-compliant	I-a	Covered	Pilot implementation experience (Pilot 5) and testing results	We use data harmonization pipelines

	data, to enable other systems to consume it				
R051	As agriculture service provider as part of Pilot 5: Connecting eDWIN to Data Markets, I would like to provide access to AIM data via standard APIs (e.g., OGC), to facilitate the interoperability with other systems/platforms. For example measurements and features via OGC SensorThings API and OGC Features APIs	I-b	Partially covered	Pilot implementation experience (Pilot 5) and testing results	We use SensorThings API generation service to automatically generate standard OGC STA from AIM compliant data, but the endpoint is not in catalogue
R052	As a data provider, I want to be able to share data in standardized form, both at the syntactic (e.g., JSON) and semantic level (e.g., AIM for agriculture that is based on OGC and W3C standards). This applies to all pilots	I-a	Covered	Pilot implementation experience (Pilot 5) and testing results	It is possible via data harmonization pipelines. And in case of AIM is based on OGC and W3C standards
R053	Convert common principles defined in the rulebook and other requirements into machine-readable policies	DS-a	Covered	Direct involvement in development	Generic principles of the Sitra rulebook model have been taken into account in machine-readable ODRL-based policy definitions.
R054	Collect machine-readable policies into a policy library, that collects together and lists machine-readable policies and their description in a human-understandable form	DS-a	Covered	Direct involvement in development	The original idea was adjusted to having policy templates for common restriction types, because all policies have to be assumed to be unique. But the original intent of being able to connect custom policies to data products without knowledge of

					coding and ODRL is covered.
R055	The framework must provide different usage policies	G-c, SO-a, IPR-a	Covered	Direct involvement in development	See notes on R054
R056	As a data provider, I would like to be able to publish part of the data as open data because of grant/funding requirements, legislations requirements or foster the reuse of the produced data	DM-a	Covered	Pilot implementation experience and testing results	The framework allows publishing the data as open data, moreover data product composition tool allows choosing what part of data will be prepared for publication
R057	As a data hub provider/domain provider (e.g. EDIH and TEF), I would like to be able to setup the dataspace for specific purpose (to share the data with specific business goals)	DS-a, FL-a	Covered	Pilot implementation experience	DATAMITE results can be used for setting up dataspace for specific purposes.
R058	The framework could be able to share data within specific data periods and ensure that they will not be available outside that timeframe	DS-c	Covered	Direct involvement in development	Time period constraint is supported by DATAMITE policies.
R059	As a pilot provider, I would like a facility to handle heterogenous data with varying access policies	DS-a	Covered	Direct involvement in development	Pilots are able to specify their policies based on their specific needs and types of data.
R062	As a data consumer, I want to be able to search/filter data and choose what to download	G-a	Covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	Search can be performed by free text, domains, owner, etc.
R063	The framework must estimate the size of a filtered dataset	G-a	Not applicable		Deemed out of scope during requirements refinement

R064	The framework could track data change through metadata	G-a	Partially covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	Changes in data artifacts in the framework are captured and seen in the lineage. Similarly, different versions of the data are kept.
R067	The connectors from the data sharing module that will be implemented in the pilot 4 must be able to provide information from the company database to the (energy) data space in order to explore new ways of providing this information	DS-d	Partially covered	Testing results, Pilot testing	R067, R068 and R069 are related and depend on other dataspace. The tests that were performed with some GAIA-X based dataspace (DATACELLAR) were partially ok, but the results were unstable due to the changes in some DATACELLAR elements
R068	The connectors from the data sharing module should be able to share the pilot 4 datasets and metadata to the (energy) data space in order to explore new ways of providing this information	DS-d	Partially covered	Testing results, Pilot testing	R067, R068 and R069 are related and depend on other dataspace. The tests that were performed with some GAIA-X based dataspace (DATACELLAR) were partially ok, but the results were unstable due to the changes in some DATACELLAR elements
R069	The connectors from the data sharing module should be configured to the data space endpoints that will be used in pilot 4 in order to be able to connect and provide	DS-d	Partially covered	Testing results, Pilot testing	R067, R068 and R069 are related and depend on other dataspace. The tests that were performed with some GAIA-X

	datasets to at least one (energy) data space				based dataspace (DATACELLAR) were partially ok, but the results were unstable due to the changes in some DATACELLAR elements
R070	Data governance and data sharing in general should be based on a set of common and shared principles, e.g. a rulebook	G-b	Partially covered	Direct involvement with pilots regarding legal and governance issues	Sitra Rulebook v.3.0 model, that has been defined by 1001 Lakes and endorsed in DSSC Toolbox, is applicable for all pilots. However, this common rulebook model has not been tailored to the needs of specific DATAMITE pilots.
R072	The platform must allow users to define and manage access control settings for their datasets, including sharing with specific individuals or groups	S-a	Covered	Pilot integration experience and testing results	Access to data (scope) can be restricted based on rules and permissions
R073	As the provider of domain service in agriculture, I would like to setup, configure and customize the Catalogue of DATAMITE framework based on DATAMITE components	FL-a	Partially covered	Pilot implementation experience (Pilot 5) and testing results	The framework can be adjusted to specific domain (e.g. agriculture) in a sense it allows configuration for specific target data space as well as create glossaries that correspond to the specific domain (domain, glossary of terms etc.)
R074	As the provider of domain service in agriculture, I would like to integrate the Catalogue of DATAMITE framework with the	S-b	Not applicable	Development of Pontus-X plugin & Operational	Full accounting system integration is out of the scope of DATAMITE framework;

	accounting system (for the transactions)			experience of Pontus-X space	publishing a data product to data market (Pontus-X) requires specifying a wallet of the data owner, but besides that, integration with wallet / transaction system of Pontus-X is out of scope.
R075	As the provider of domain service in agriculture, I would like to integrate the Catalogue of DATAMITE framework with the external billing system (like PayPal)	DM-a	Not applicable	Development of Pontus-X plugin & Operational experience of Pontus-X space	Full accounting system integration is out of the scope of DATAMITE framework; publishing a data product to data market (Pontus-X) requires specifying a wallet of the data owner, but besides that, integration with wallet / transaction system of Pontus-X is out of scope.
R076	The framework won't be able to create data spaces from scratch	DS-a	Not applicable		The framework can connect to dataspace, but it is not its goal to create them.
R079	The framework requires a data Catalogue that can be used by users to find data assets in their system	G-a	Covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	Search can be performed by free text, domains, owner, etc.
R080	The framework requires a data Catalogue that can be used to edit or add information to data assets in the system, e.g. linking data entities/fields with terms in the data glossary	G-a	Covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	Datasets can be uploaded, and their metadata can be edited through the user interface
R082	The framework requires that the data Catalogue can be linked to the data quality	G-a	Covered	Participated in the	Data is profiled when ingested. Additionally, user-

	functionalities to run the corresponding routines and evaluate the data asset accordingly			development. Validated.	defined rules can be defined and evaluated afterwards.
R083	The framework requires a data dictionary for each dataset that displays a set of basic indicators, that have been agreed beforehand, and that offer basic information about the dataset	G-a	Covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	The number of business vocabularies is not limited. New vocabularies can be added at any point to the glossary. Similarly, vocabularies can be extended with new terms at any moment.
R084	The data glossary must be able to import existing vocabularies. To import them they must be in a format that is friendly to the glossary	G-a	Covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	The framework allows importing existing vocabularies from CSV files. It expects a collection of terms with ID, name, description, abbreviation.
R085	The data glossary must be able to group the vocabularies per domain. A vocabulary may be related to more than one domain	G-a	Covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	A vocabulary can be linked to several domains
R087	The framework must consider that data assets may be composed of data artifacts	G-a	Covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	Structured datasets are composed of artifacts. Databases follow a similar approach, composed of tables and columns. Non-structured data are slightly different due to its nature.
R088	The data Catalogue and the data dictionary must facilitate the addition of metadata and information, in general, at a fine or	G-a	Covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	Different types of metadata can be included in the datasets/artifacts in an easy and

	detailed level enough to achieve a sufficient level of interpretation of the datasets				intuitive way through the user interface
R089	The framework should provide basic data lineage functionalities to record and make accessible the origin of the data and the processes through which they pass when it applies	CO-b, G-a	Covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	Basic data lineage functionalities are included in the framework and visible in the catalogue
R090	End user must have the capability to access a centralized data Catalogue, where he/she will be able to identify who is the data owner of each dataset, what are the underline data, their definition and their data types, and last but not least to capture data lineage. Solution must offer a full Catalogue of business and technical metadata	G-a	Covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	The catalogue allows the inclusion of descriptive metadata informing the user of different aspects, from ownership, to descriptions and quality or lineage.
R091	The framework must clarify who has control over the data and how ownership rights can be preserved to create a fair and transparent data market	SO-b, IPR-a	Covered	Direct involvement in development	Through usage policies (Policy Engine)
R093	Solution should provide the capability to update technical or business metadata, by integrating and capturing the latest view from metadata repository	G-a	Covered	Testing results, Pilot testing	Through the DATAMITE framework frontend
R094	The framework requires the implementation of an efficient metadata repository to store and index rich metadata to enable rapid search and retrieval of asset information	G-a	Covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	DATAMITE uses Apache Atlas as internal metadata repository.

R095	The framework must provide search option for metadata	G-a	Covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	Search can be performed by free text, domains, owner, etc.
R096	The framework should be able to map the connection between related datasets	G-a	Covered	Pilot implementation experience, Testing results	
R098	The framework (data quality module) must evaluate the quality of a dataset based on standard quality indicators	DQ-a	Covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	The framework includes a KPI library, easy to extend with new metrics, that already considers a wide number of metrics for different types of structured and non-structured data.
R099	A set of data quality indicators must be defined such that they are used by the data profiler and data dictionary. These indicators can be statistical indicators (e.g., mean, histograms), describe the type of dataset or others	DQ-b	Covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	The framework includes a KPI library, easy to extend with new metrics, that already considers a wide number of metrics for different types of structured and non-structured data.
R100	The framework should provide data quality monitoring of underline data (sources and relevant pipelines). It should offer the capability to execute business defined data quality rules in order to monitor key data elements (KDE)	DQ-b	Partially covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	Users can define user-defined rules to monitor particular business aspects on the data. These rules can be evaluated at any moment.
R101	The framework must implement basic and advanced quality mechanisms, including additional KPIs, such as the	DQ-a	Covered	Testing results	

	detection of data biases, advanced statistics, etc.				
R102	There must be a description language (DSL) powerful and expressive enough to describe quality metadata - DSLQ	G-a	Covered	Direct involvement in development	DDQV - adapted vocabulary from DQV.
R103	The searches allowed in the Catalogue should consider parameters referring to dimensions or quality indicators	G-c	Not covered		It is something that has been considered, although, to properly perform this search the use of LLMs was required, overcomplicating its implementation.
R105	The framework should have efficient provisions for checking data quality (e.g., to detect concept drift, missing data, inconsistent data, anomalies, outliers, completeness, validity, timeliness, consistency, etc.)	DQ-b	Covered	Operational Usage, Testing results	Data quality pipeline is implemented for structured datasets and unstructured data with ability to define user-defined quality rules
R106	The framework should ensure that data is regularly updated and monitored to ensure it is current	DQ-a	Partially covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	Data is uploaded manually. The only data that can be regularly updated in an automated way is streaming data. Streaming data has options to define how it should be consolidated (size or time) and the date when data was uploaded can be checked in the catalog
R108	The Data supporting tools module should include tools that provide information about fairness/bias of a	DQ-c	Covered	Testing results	

	dataset following indications of EU regulations				
R109	Data sharing: The usage policy should be available on data publishing to EU portals	DS-c, DM-b	Covered	Testing results, Pilot testing	
R110	As a user of the data, I would like to know if the data is validated/curated and what is the date of validation	DM-a	Covered	Pilot testing results	There is information about edits, data quality (e.g. empty rows., duplicates), defined quality rules
R111	End product should provide data quality reports allowing business and technical users to monitor data quality progress and keep them informed concerning the status of data that are ready to be consumed	DQ-a	Covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	Data products are profiled and treated as any dataset in the system, meaning that user-defined rules can also be applied and evaluated
R112	Interfaces to compare the quality of different datasets, considering a future provision to third parties, through exchange or sale	DQ-a, DQ-b	Partially covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	The framework includes a "general quality score" that allows to compare datasets. However, its use in the description of a data product depends on the target ecosystem. Including this information would not be a problem from DATAMITE side.
R113	Transformation pipeline system should be implemented. This tool should be totally adaptable in order to accomplish publication requirements	DS-b	Covered	Pilot implementation experience, Testing results	
R116	Procedures must be provided to facilitate the definition of roles in data management and guarantee compliance with	F-c, G-c, SD-a	Covered	Pilot implementation experience, Testing results	

	data accessibility policies designed				
R117	A tool to define fine-grained data access policies about who, what, how and when has access to data (clearly defined security policies and role-based permissions)	F-c, SD-a	Covered	Pilot implementation experience, Testing results	
R118	The framework should have the capability to control/monitor internal users access across all data sources, and enable reviewing which type of data has been accessed by whom, tracking users actions and alerting possible privacy issues	U-b, S-a	Covered	Testing results, Pilot testing, Direct involvement in development	
R119	Datasets owners must have control in two different points related to the dataset publishing: firstly, owners must have access control (who can access the dataset) and secondly, owners must have visualization control (who can view metadata in marketplace tool)	DM-d	Covered	Pilot implementation experience, Testing results	
R120	The framework should ensure and enforce data sovereignty on the IDSA connectors	SO-a	Covered	Direct involvement in development	EDC connectors
R121	As a data provider, I want to be able to share data inside a sandbox owned by me (access control framework)	S-a	Not applicable		Deemed out of scope during requirements refinement
R122	The data sharing module must include an efficient tool that uses the appropriate storage technologies (e.g., databases, blockchain) to	DS-c, SO-c	Covered	Direct involvement in development	

	support the secure storage of usage contracts				
R123	The data sharing module must describe the permissions and obligations of participants involved in data exchange through contracts	DM-b, DS-c, IPR-a, IPR-c	Covered	Direct involvement in development	
R124	The data sharing module should perpetually monitor the evaluation of usage enforcement	E-a, U-b	Covered	Direct involvement in development, Testing results	
R125	As a System Manager, I want the data components that interact with raw data to be deployed in EDP internal network, so that I comply with applicable corporate security policies	C-c	Covered	Pilot implementation experience, Testing results	
R126	The connectors from the data sharing modules to be implemented in pilot 4 should not require inbound firewall configuration (e.g. expose VM port to the internet)	DS-d	Covered	Direct involvement in development	
R130	The framework (data support tools) could check if the anonymization of a dataset was successful	S-d	Covered	Testing results, Pilot testing, Direct involvement in development	
R133	As a data hub provider/domain provider, I would like to make sure the data are shared in secure way (access control, authorization, secure protocol for data accessing)	S-a	Covered	Testing results, Pilot testing, Direct involvement in development	
R138	The platform should be integrated with an IAM solution such as Keycloak or similar	S-a	Covered	Direct involvement in the development	Keycloak is implemented in the authentication process
R139	A storage technology is required to receive the data	C-a	Covered	Participated in the	The framework uses MinIO

	captured with the data ingestion mechanisms. This may include a landing layer			development. Validated.	internally to store datasets
R141	The framework must provide a homogeneous/standard process to ingest data in bulk or streaming	F-b	Covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	The framework includes pipelines for bulk data (accepting different types of files) and for streaming data (accepting different protocols). Moreover, streaming plugins follow a template, so it is easy to extend this to other protocols.
R143	A connector to the company data lake must be developed in the data support tools module in order to ingest and process the datasets for the pilot 4	F-b	Partially covered	Pilot implementation experience, Testing results	As mentioned in R193, constraints in the deployment of the framework on the first VM delayed the testing of this component. The connector was developed, however it is still to be tested.
R144	The framework must be able to discover existing datasets stored in different storage technologies	F-b, C-a	Covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	A series of connectors have been designed to enable the ingestion from streams and databases (e.g., Kafka, MQTT, MySQL, MongoDB, Cassandra, Azure, etc.)
R146	The framework could support accounting / telemetry functionalities	DS-b	Not applicable	Direct involvement in development	The framework can support the relevant functionalities, provided they are supported by the integrated data ecosystem.

					However, none of the currently integrated ecosystems supports accounting or telemetry functionalities.
R147	The data and its metadata must be persisted appropriately to its type and source/origin, in addition to being annotated with other considerations of sovereignty, privacy, openness, quality, provenance, etc. and also have a set of functionalities that allow discovering and consult this information	G-a	Covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	Data is not transformed upon its ingestion, preserving types. Data coming from streaming or DB queries are being persisted using standard formats such as CSV. All data is complemented with different types of metadata (automatically or manually added), such as quality, and its lineage is preserved. Similarly, data sovereignty policies or information is preserved on data publications (which is the stage where this information is added)
R149	As a pilot provider, I would like to have data searching and filtering capability based on predefined criteria (like statistics about the data quality for each dataset)	G-a, DQ-b	Covered	Pilot implementation experience and testing results	
R150	The platform frontend should be optimized for mobile. The mobile may	U-d	Not applicable	Participated in the development.	It was finally considered that DATAMITE framework is not

	offer less options but it should be developed				thought to be used from a mobile, but from a desktop.
R152	We must have multiple user tiers, with multiple roles associated. Users must be able to create an account (at least for the lower tier). Others would be managed by admins	F-b, S-a	Partially covered	Direct involvement in the development	At the frontend we don't have a code for this permissions differences.
R153	All data models should be created as independent components to be easily integrated in the platform	FL-a, FL-b, G-b	Covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	
R154	The platform must provide a public privacy and cookie policy	SD-b	Covered	Direct involvement in the development	The templates are designed and developed on the frontend and backoffice level. They can be edited at any time.
R155	We should be able to monitor the platform health in one place (individual services status, APIs availability, other)	E-c, SM-b	Not covered	Participated in the development.	Currently under investigation, probably use Grafana
R156	A storage technology is required to store the data assets stored in the system. The storage technology may or may not be the same used to receive the data from the ingestion mechanisms	C-a	Covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	A MinIO is used to store data coming from bulk files, streaming, or queries internally. Databases are not stored, just linked.
R157	The framework data ingestion mechanisms in streaming should accept multiple formats/protocols (e.g. Kafka, MQTT, or others)	C-b, I-a	Covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	The framework can ingest different types of data using plugins for streaming data. These plugins follow a template, and the process is easy to extend to new protocols.

R158	The solution must facilitate data connectors with core traditional databases (e.g., Oracle, Microsoft, SAP), ensuring seamless connectivity with the majority of operational systems currently in use. These connectors are to be designed to support integration with both on-premises and cloud infrastructures, equipped with functionalities to update or select tables and columns from the datastore	C-a	Covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	A series of connectors have been designed to enable the ingestion from streams and databases (e.g., Kafka, MQTT, MySQL, MongoDB, Cassandra, Azure, etc.)
R159	The solution should enable data connectors with non-relational databases, big data infrastructures, and data storages (e.g., Cloudera, S3 AWS, ADLS Azure, HBase), promoting connectivity with both current and anticipated big data infrastructure organizations. These connectors are expected to support integration across on-premises and cloud infrastructures, with the solution's design aiming for generality and ease of integrating additional databases	C-a, SM-a	Covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	A series of connectors have been designed to enable the ingestion from streams and databases (e.g., Kafka, MQTT, MySQL, MongoDB, Cassandra, Azure, etc.)
R160	All of the developed components from the different modules must be compatible with the Azure cloud (E-REDES infrastructure system) so that they can be integrated to deploy the demonstration	C-c, SM-a	Covered	Pilot implementation experience, Testing results	Initial implementations of the framework were compatible with the Azure cloud infrastructure. Newer implementations are also compatible, however remain to be tested due to

					constraints in the creation and access to the newer scaled up internal VM.
R162	Connection with different persistence technologies must be present (e.g. PostgreSQL, MariaDB, MongoDB, Cassandra, Elasticsearch, etc.)	C-a	Covered	Tested and validated	Different plugins have been implemented to connect to different database technologies (e.g. PostgreSQL, MariaDB, MySQL, MinIO, Cassandra, etc.)
R163	The framework must be able to store datasets, at least, as objects (e.g., S3-like storage)	C-a; C-c	Covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	The framework uses MinIO internally to store datasets
R165	The platform frontend must be compatible with modern web browsers	C-a	Covered	Pilot experience and testing results	Frontend is responsive and works without issues on browsers we've been using
R166	Set up continuous integration (CI) tools and processes	FL-b, SM-c	Covered	Operational Usage	
R167	Establish CI workflows to guide the integration	FL-b, SM-c	Covered	Testing results	
R168	Implement version control to manage the source code and track changes	SM-c	Covered	Operational Usage	
R169	Provide comprehensive documentation and guidelines for the CI tools and processes	S-a	Covered	Technical documentation	
R170	System should offer capability for upgrading the whole solution (or part of this) enabling the correction of possible bugs and/or upgrading its current capabilities	SM-c	Covered	Testing results	

R172	The Catalogue that is defined in the DATAMITE framework, should annotate/publish its services adequately, so that they can be compiled in GAIA-X/IDS data spaces	I-a	Covered	Direct involvement in development	
R173	The platform design could be aligned with low carbon guidelines for web development	SD-b	Covered	Direct involvement in development	The accessibility and ecograder are being taken into account.
R174	It could be possible to define the conditions in which the data will be provided (establish some minimums/requirements in terms of quality, periodicity, precision, etc.)	DS-a	Covered	Direct involvement in development	Through the policy engine, integrated with the EDC connector, and the 3 policies developed (Time interval, Location, and Purpose)
R176	System should be able to operate both on prem and on cloud infrastructure, allowing organization to select preferred type based on the overall IT strategy	C-c	Covered	Operational Usage	As documented in D5.4 (Table 1) some pilots utilized dedicated virtual machines on cloud platforms, such as Azure or Google Cloud, while others relied on in-house solutions
R179	The platform frontend should be considered high-performing under PageSpeed Insights tool	E-b, E-c, SM-b, U-c	Partially covered	Direct involvement in development	The performance on desktop is at 85. The URL is on internal development hosting.
R180	Clear criteria must be defined to evaluate the quality of the DATAMITE framework	Defining them should be documented in reports	Covered		
R181	To ensure easy and reusable implementation of some standard operations like anonymization, the framework should provide libraries. It is important that these mechanisms are well	S-a, SD-a	Covered	Pilot implementation experience, Testing results	

	documented and designed in a user-friendly way to allow developers a seamless integration process				
R182	The system should provide a unified user interface for business users to access core operations, including data and metadata. An elevated view for administrators is essential for full functionality access, with a key system feature being the transparency of policies and access rules. A dedicated form is advised to clearly present these restrictions to administrators. The complexity of integrating more databases necessitates a clear and user-friendly UI for efficient policy orchestration and monitoring	U-a	Partially covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	DATAMITE includes two tools related to this purpose. On the one hand, authentication and authorization is implemented using Keycloak, being possible to define roles and rules. Additionally, thinking on sharing data in data spaces, the framework includes a tool to define ODRL-based access and usage control policies.
R183	Training material that enables companies better understanding the roles and responsibilities of individual internal departments within the data cycle	SD-a	Partially covered	Pilot implementation experience and testing results	The framework allows specifying what roles have control and access to data on specific data cycle
R184	The system must be easy to use to facilitate its adoption by non-technical personnel	U-a	Covered	Participated in the development. Validated.	The user interfaces have been designed and implemented with the focus on the user, putting usability first.
R187	The platform must be compliant with ADA and WCAG under European guidelines	U-d	Partially covered	Direct involvement in the development	In the end of the development stages, these metrics are being constantly enhanced

R188	The platform could support multiple languages for user interfaces and content to cater to a diverse user base	U-d	Partially covered	Participated in the development.	This option is implemented on the framework backoffice. It's not aligned if the idea is to have pages translated, but it's ready if needed.
R189	The open source resulting framework must be fully downloadable without any dependency with a proprietary component	U-a	Covered	https://gitlab.eclipse-pse.org/eclipse-research-labs/datamite-project	The whole DATAMITE framework is open source, being available in the project public repository in the Eclipse Research Labs in GitLab. All the DATAMITE components, 100% of them, are open source, licensed under MIT license. Great achievement from the open-source perspective
R190	None of the mandatory (vs. optional) library dependencies must be based on Strong Copyleft license (e.g. GPL or AGPL)	C-a, IPR-	Covered	https://gitlab.eclipse-pse.org/eclipse-research-labs/datamite-project	All the 3rd party dependencies have been checked periodically during the project lifetime, and the critical ones were raised in issues in Gitlab. They were cleared (in the last round of IP check, at the end of 2025).
R191	Each source code files, script files, config files, must have their copyright header setup properly indicating the owner (institution or organization), the license selected, and, optionally, the developer ID. The license file must be included	C-a, IPR-	Covered	https://gitlab.eclipse-pse.org/eclipse-research-labs/datamite-project	During the project, there has been a procedure in place in which ECL offered guidance with the copyright headers and added them as a template for the developers to keep adding

	in each repository created by the project				them systematically. A very high percentage of the source code files include a copyright header
R193	In order to deploy the demonstration an Azure-based sandbox must be created in the E-REDES IT systems	F-a	Partially covered	Testing results, Pilot testing	A sandbox resource group was created in the internal unmanaged domain. For initial deployments and tests of the framework a Windows-based VM was created. Early tests were successful. For the newer versions of the framework, the previous setup had limitations and was unable to support the deployment and hosting of the framework. To overcome that issue, and to not compromise the testing of the components, an ITI hosted VM was used for the remainder of the project. A new internal Ubuntu VM was requested to try and replicate the ITI implementation.
R194	The data support module should provide a generic anonymization tool	SD-a, S-a, S-b	Covered	Testing results, Pilot testing, Direct involvement in development	

R195	The anonymization tool provides a feature that informs the user about the most suitable anonymization technique for each field in the imported data	S-a	Covered	Testing results, Pilot testing, Direct involvement in development	
R196	The data sharing module should ensure integrity in the data sharing process	DS-d	Covered	Direct involvement in development	
R197	The data sharing module must provide a monitoring and auditing tool within the framework to transparently oversee transactions with external users, ensuring visibility and clarity in the handling of sensitive data sharing	CO-b, DS-b, E-a	Covered	Pilot implementation experience	
R198	The framework should provide a workflow tool to orchestrate the processes needed to create a data product from a (set of) operational data source(s)	P-c	Covered	Testing results, Pilot testing	
R199	Check security compliance requirements and track user activities and access leveraging on auditing and reporting capabilities	S-b	Covered	Pilot implementation experience, Testing results	
R200	The anonymization tool provides a feature that informs the user about sensitive and non-sensitive values in the imported dataset	S-a	Covered	Testing results, Pilot testing, Direct involvement in development	
R201	The Framework must aggregate data from various sources	F-b	Covered	Testing results, Pilot testing, Direct involvement in development	
R202	The framework is designed to facilitate the creation of a new data product by	F-b	Covered	Testing results, Pilot testing, Direct	

	extracting a subset from the original dataset			involvement in development	
R203	The framework could facilitate the exploration of data providing an overview of the dataset	F-b	Covered	Pilot implementation experience, Testing results	
R204	The framework could log the data preprocessing actions (e.g. aggregation, anonymization)	P-c	Covered	Direct involvement in development, Testing results	
R205	The framework could enable using common standardized (e.g. based on ISO/IEC 9075:2023) SQL queries to different RDBMS that are currently in use	C-b	Covered	Testing results, Pilot testing, Direct involvement in development	